

Correlation of Alcohol Addiction and Disruptive Behaviours among University Undergraduates in Enugu State University of Science and Technology

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ABSTRACT: The study aimed at determining the correlation of alcohol addiction and disruptive behaviour among undergraduates in Enugu state university of Science and Technology (ESUT), Enugu, Nigeria. The study was carried out in Enugu State using a correlation design research method. Two research questions and two null hypotheses guided the study. The population for the study consists of 26,000 regular undergraduates of Enugu state University. The sample for the study consists of 360 undergraduates. A Multi-stage sample approach was employed in selecting the sample size as follows; first, simple random sampling technique was used to choose ten (10) faculties from Enugu State University. This gave a total of 360 university undergraduate students comprising of 200 males and 160 females. The instrument used for data collection was a structured questionnaire developed by the researcher. The instrument was structured using a four point rating scale and was face validated by three experts, in Faculty of Education, Enugu State University of Sciences and Technology. Cronbach Alpha reliability coefficient was used to determine the reliability obtained from the five sections of the instrument ranged from 0.96 to 0.85 while the overall reliability coefficient of the whole instrument was 0.73. Out of 369 copies of questionnaire distributed, 334 copies were properly filled and returned which represent 92.78% return rate. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions while t-test statistics was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The result of the findings indicated that alcohol addiction leads undergraduate to a great extent in rival group clashes, armed robbery, vandalism and sexual harassment in Enugu State. The null hypotheses tested showed no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female students. Based on the findings, it was recommended among others that there should be public enlightenment on the effect of drug and alcohol abuse among the students thereby putting up strong rules and regulation against alcohol and substance abuse among students.

KEY WORDS: Correlation, Alcohol, Addiction, Disruptive, Behavior, Undergraduates.

INTRODUCTION

Alcohol (ethanol or ethyl alcohol) is the ingredient found in beer, wine and spirits that causes drunkenness. Alcohol is formed when yeast ferments (breaks down without oxygen) the sugars in different foods. For example, wine is made from the sugar in grapes, beer from the sugar in malted barley (a type of grain), and cider from the sugar in apples, vodka from the sugar in potatoes, beets or other plants.

Alcohol is classed as a 'sedative hypnotic' drugs, which means it acts to depress the central nervous system at high doses. At lower doses, alcohol can act as a stimulant, inducing feelings of euphoria and talkativeness, but drinking too much alcohol at one session can lead to drowsiness, respiratory depression (where breathing becomes slow, shallow or stops entirely), coma or even death. As well as its acute and potentially lethal sedative effect at high doses, alcohol has effects on every organ in the body and these effects depend on the blood alcohol concentration (BAC) overtime.

Alcohol is a depressant drug that slows down various sections of the brain and the central nervous system. This affects one's ability to control one's behaviour and one's bodily functions, like thinking, talking, walking and even breathing. Alcohol is also described as a psychoactive drug. This means a drug that affects the mind, or mental processes. Alcohol addiction is a potential problems that changes the way the brain works. It causes negative emotions, impulsive behaviour, cravings and withdrawal symptoms.

Alcohol addiction is defined as a chronic state in which one's body and mind become dependent on alcohol. Alcohol addiction is an extremely serious problem that claims millions around the world for various reasons. From the elderly, to university students,

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to the middle-aged and even adolescents, alcohol addiction has managed to invade and destroy the lives of even the most promising individuals. Alcohol addiction among university undergraduates represents a major global public health concern due to its immediate and long-term physical and mental health effects. Davison, (2004) and Dumbili (2012) have found that alcohol is fermented liquor such as beer, wine, or distilled spirit, which contains ethyl alcohol ($\text{CH}_3 \text{CH}_2 \text{OH}$), and serves as an intoxicating agent (Encyclopedia Britannica, 2010). Alcohol beverage includes beers, wines, and spirits.

Alcohol is taken for different reasons. While many drink alcohol during social functions like birthday, wedding and child dedication celebrations; others drink alcohol to feel happy or for the excitement and fun that is often associated with it. Many university undergraduates apparently take alcohol to show that they 'belong' - as a result of peer influence. Curtin, Patrick, Lang, Cacioppo, Birbhaner, (2001) and Mohamed, (2013), believed that addiction to alcohol lowers inhibitions and affect negatively the ability to judge the consequences of people's actions. Alcohol also affects the normal functioning of the brain. Dumbili (2012) observed that excessive drinking is not only a major health concern in the long-term, it can lead to immediate tragedies such as assaults, injury, arrest and even death. When people are under the influence of alcohol they can do things which they would not have done if they were in their right senses. It is discovered that alcohol is responsible for more than 100,000 deaths in the United States of America each year. (Nevid and Rathus, 2005). Arrington, (2004), Nevid and Rathus, (2005) and Kelvin (2011) observed that most of the university undergraduates who are addicted to alcohol also partake in violent activities. This may seem to be the case with some of the violent activities and demonstrations by undergraduates of different universities in Nigeria. Some of the students who are involved in disruptive behaviours might have taken alcohol before their actions or even during their actions and then use the bottles of the drinks to inflict injuries on their victims. According to WHO, (2015) heavy alcohol intake by university undergraduates directly affect their cognitive and physical function. It can reduce self control as well as adversely affect the ability to process information and assess risks. This entails that heavy alcohol intake is a factor for perpetrating violence by undergraduates.

Disruption has become an issue of great concern in the world today. Its impact is felt almost in every nation of the world. Disruption is the use of physical force with the intent to injure, abuse, damage or destroy. It is intense, turbulent, or furious and often violent action or force. Disruption is defined by the World Health Organization as "the intentional use of physical force or power, threatened or actual against oneself, another person, a group or community, which either results in or has a high likelihood of resulting in injury, death, psychological harm, maldevelopment or deprivation. According to Hornby (2012), Disruptive is behaviour that involves the use of physical force intended to hurt, damage, or kill someone. Disruption is an interruption to a regular flow or sequence of something, it is a continuing act of disorder. (Egbo, 2021).

Nigeria has witnessed disruption in different forms and by different people. These disruptive behaviours include religious intolerance, assassination, rival group clashes, arm robbery, political crises, vandalism, kidnapping, sexual harassment and ethnic conflicts. More than a million people lose their lives and suffer injuries annually. Huge amount of properties are destroyed as a result of disruption, (World Health Organization, WHO, 2015). Disruption poses great challenges to the peace and human development of a nation.

In many societies, Disruption is so dominant that it thwarts hopes of economic and social development. Most people who live with violence day in, day out assume that it is an intrinsic part of human existence (WHO, 2015). University undergraduates are those greatly involved in disruptive acts across the world. For the purpose of this study, the university undergraduates are seen as those who are in the University for their First Degree Studies. Usually, they are within the age of adolescent and early adulthood, (18 to 24 years). Violence are all forms of life threatening and harmful activities associated with the university undergraduates. Mohammed, (2013) noted that shooting, inter-tribal fighting, rival group clashes, vandalism, sexual harassment, and arm robbery are examples of disruptive act among university undergraduates.

Sexual harassment is intimidation, bullying or coercion of a sexual nature, or the unwelcome or inappropriate promise of rewards in exchange for sexual favour (Egbo, 2021). It is unwanted conduct of a sexual nature which has the purpose or effect of violating someone's dignity, or creating an intimidating, hostile, degrading, humiliating or offensive environment. It covers indecent or suggestive remarks, unwanted touching, requests or demands for sex and the dissemination of pornography. Echiegu (2011), the most common adverse consequence of sexual harassment/victimization was psychological distress, followed by poor academic performance and sexually transmitted infection. Sexual abuse is a global public health problem that cuts across social class, cultures, and tribes has permeated the fabrics of tertiary institutions and many work places as long as humans have reasons to interact. Sexual abuse may take many forms and vary in terms of frequency, duration, invasiveness of the acts involved, and the use of force or coercion. Both male and female are affected, though most of the cases occur among female, especially undergraduates. Studies have shown that sexual abuse have negative impacts on the physical, social and mental health of the victim. Some of the consequences include reproductive health problems like unwanted pregnancy, sexually transmitted diseases/HIV, all forms of injuries, depression, anxiety, social isolation, loss of self-esteem, distrust of others, substance abuse, post-traumatic disorder, disability and even death. The problem of sexual abuse against female undergraduates in our tertiary institutions has remained

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largely unaddressed, it prevents these students from attaining their maximum intellectual, emotional and educational potential. Various forms of sexual abuse have been reported to occur among undergraduates of Ebonyi State University which include rape (attempted or completed), unwanted sexual advances, demanding sex in return for favour, sexual abuse of mentally or physically disabled people and grabbing of sensitive body parts among others. Despite the problems caused by sexual violence, majority of the cases that were not reported has led to rising cases of abuse especially in our universities for the culprit to move freely thereby worsening the state of the abused females.

Vandalism is an attitude or mode of expression which aims to try to destroy a certain culture and art as well as other people's heritage. Vandalism is typically defined as a willful act intended to alter, destroy, deface or significantly change another person's property. Vandalism in schools may take various forms, from writing in books to writing on the desks, from marring walls to smashing windows, from cutting up school bus seats to taking school furniture apart. While the school chancellor is typically responsible for dealing with student vandals, school authorities also play an important role in preventing vandalism by attending to the reasons for the behaviour such as talking to the students about caring for others' property, examine the student's motivation, model respect for school property and require the students to make amends. Armed robbery is forceful taking of someone's belongings from him or her with a weapon.

Disruption among university undergraduates not only affects them but also their families, friends and communities. It is high in institutions of learning, where students in their youthful ages get involved in different forms of disruptive activities leading to injuries, destruction of property and sometimes resulting in death of people. Many undergraduates (male and female) who involve in disruption do it for different reasons, to press home their demand, to terrorize others, to show superiority and to suppress rival groups. Violent behaviours among university undergraduates may have been as a result of substance abuse. It seems that there is a connection between alcohol use and disruptive behaviour. Alcohol use and disruptive behaviour are being carried out by male and female of undergraduates of Enugu State University, this means that there was no gender difference among them.

Gender is the fact of being either male or female, a fact used culturally to determine the roles or pattern of behaviour and attitudes which either of the genders is expected to exhibit. It refers to different characteristics of men and women that are socially determined. Gender is relative and refers not simply to male or female but to the relationship between them. Gender also refers to the economic, social and cultural attributes and opportunities associated with being male or female at a particular point in time (Jolly and Esplen, 2008). In this study the undergraduates are male and female. Male and female undergraduates of university are also involved in alcohol intake and disruptive behaviours.

The extent to which these disruptive activities are influenced by alcohol intake has not been adequately and specifically addressed. Hence this work tries to fill the gap by trying to find out the correlate of alcohol and disruptive behaviours using Enugu State University as the area of study.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Disruptive behaviour among university undergraduates is rampant in the Nigerian society. Behaviours like sexual harassment, rioting, fighting, intimidation, cult clashes and quarrelling are witnessed among the university undergraduates. These disruptive behaviours sometimes result to sad consequences like injury on the victims and perpetrators, damage of properties and loss of life. This undesirable state of affairs is a source of worry to many people in the society. The government is concerned; authorities of universities are disturbed; the students themselves are affected a lot in their academics and life style. Resources, both human and materials are lost because of this menace. If this situation continues, the economic development of the country will be staked. The university undergraduates that are addicted to alcohol are often associated to the disruptive behaviours. The researcher thus, wants to find out the extent to which alcohol addiction and disruptive behaviours are related. Thus, the problem of this study is to find out the correlate of alcohol addiction and disruptive behaviours among University Undergraduates in Enug State University of Science and Technology..

Purpose of the Study. Specifically, the study sought to determine:

1. The correlate of alcohol addiction and rival group clashes among students of Enugu State University of Science and Technology.
2. The correlate of alcohol addiction and sexual harassment among students of Enugu State University of Science and Technology.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the correlate of alcohol addiction and rival group clashes among students of Enugu State University of Science and Technology?

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2. What is the correlate of alcohol addiction and sexual harassment among students of Enugu State University of Science and Technology?

Hypotheses;The following hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance and also guided the study.

1. There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female undergraduates of Enugu State University on the correlation between alcohol addiction and rival group clashes among students of Enugu University.
2. There is no significance difference between the mean ratings of male and female undergraduates of Enugu State University on the correlation between alcohol addiction and sexual harassment among students of the University.

Method

The researcher adopted a correlational research design. A correlational design is a design that seeks to establish the relationship that exists between two or more variables that indicates the direct and magnitude of the relationship between the variables (Nworgu, 2012).

A correlational design is considered appropriate for the study because it seeks to establish a relationship between two variables, namely; alcohol addiction and disruptive behaviours. This study was carried out in Enugu state. Enugu state is one of the thirty six states of Nigeria. It is located in south east part of Nigeria. It is inhabited and populated primarily by the Igbos. The state is divided into seventeen (17) local governments Area. It is home to six higher institutions of learning: Enugu State University of Science and Technology, Enugu (ESUT); University of Nigeria Nsukka (UNN); Peace Land University (PLU); Godfrey Okonye University (GOU), Coal City University (CCU); College of Education Technical (ECET) and Ehamufu College of Education Sciences Ezzamgbo. The undergraduates of Enugu of Science and Technology were used with 11 faculties and 56 departments. The population for the study consists of 26,000 regular undergraduates of the University. It comprises two campuses of Enugu and Agbani. The sample for the study consists of 360 undergraduates which is 92.78%. A Multi-stage approach was employed in selecting the sample size as follows; first, simple random sampling technique was used to choose ten faculties out of 11 faculties in the University. Faculties that were chosen are; Management, Arts, Basic Medical Science, Biological Science, Clinical Medicine, Education, Health Science and technology, Management Science, Physical science and Social sciences. 20 male undergraduates and 16 female undergraduates were chosen from each faculty. This yields a total of 360 university undergraduate students that is 200 males and 160 females. This form the sample for the study. The instrument used for data collection is a self structured questionnaire developed by the researcher validated by three experts in Education. The instrument is called Alcohol Addiction and Disruptive Behaviour Questionnaire (AADBQ). The questionnaire has two sections: Section A is for personal data of the respondents while section B contains 18 items. Section B sought to assess the correlate of alcohol addiction and disruptive behaviour among Enugu State University Undergraduates. This also has 4 point response options which ranged from very high extent to very low extent and had weighted values of 4, 3, 2, and 1 respectively. Section B has 4 items coined to address research question 1, section C consist of 5 items which addressed research question 2. The reliability of the instrument was established by the use of Cronbach Alpha (Uzoagulu, 2011). The instrument yielded the following reliability coefficients; 0.81, 0.80, 0.96 and 0.85 for sections A, B, C and D respectively. The grand coefficient was 0.73, indicating that the instrument was reliable for use in data collection. 360 copies of questionnaire were administered and finally we were able to retrieve 334 copies signify 92.78% return rate.

Data were analyzed using Pearson Moment Correlation Coefficient (r) and t-test statistic. To do these, mean and standard deviation were calculated first. Hence, the response option of Very High Extent (VHE), High Extent (HE), Low Extent (LE), and Very Low Extent (VLE) were weighted as 4, 3, 2, and 1, respectively.

Research questions were answered using Pearson correlation coefficient which indicated the relationship between the variables. Correlation coefficient values from 1 to 9 showed negative relationship, zero (0) showed no relationship 1 to 4 showed weak positive relationship. 5 to 9 showed strong positive relationship while 1 showed perfect relationship. Finally the t-test statistics was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. When the calculated t-value is more than the critical value, the hypothesis was rejected, but if the calculated t-value is less than the critical value the hypothesis was not rejected as stated.

DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

Research Question 1

What is the correlate of alcohol addiction and rival group clashes among students of Enugu State University of Science and Technology?

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Table 1: Correlation test for correlate of alcohol addiction and rival group clashes among students of Enugu State University of Science and Technology.

		Alcohol Addiction	Rival group Clashes
Alcohol Addiction	Pearson Correlation	1	.836
	Sig.	-	.000
	N	334	334
Rival Group Clashes	Pearson Correlation	.836	1
	Sig.	.000	-
	N	334	334

From table 1 above, the correlation coefficient between alcohol addiction and rival group clashes is .836. This indicates a strong positive correlation, implying that alcohol addiction leads to rival group clashes. Hence, the tendency for an alcohol addict to engage in rival group clashes is very high.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female undergraduates of Enugu State University of Science and Technology on the correlation between alcohol addiction and rival group clashes among students of the University.

Table 2: t-test analyses for hypothesis 1.

Variables	N	\bar{X}	SD	Df	t-cal	t-crit	Decision
Male	183	2.66	0.79	323	0.71	<u>+1.96</u>	Not significant (Do not reject hypothesis)
Female	151	2.65	0.55				

The t-test result in table 2 shows that t-calculated value is 0.71 while t-critical value is +1.96. This means that t-calculated is less than t-critical at a df of 332 and a significant level of 0.05. Going by the decision rule, no significant difference was found in the mean scores of male and female student undergraduates of Enugu State University of Science and Technology on correlation between alcohol addiction and rival group clashes among students of the University.

Research Question 2

What is the relationship between alcohol addiction and sexual harassment among students of Enugu State University?

Table 3. Correlation test for relationship between alcohol addiction and sexual harassment among students of Enugu State University.

		Alcohol Addiction	Sexual Harassment
Alcohol Addiction	Pearson Correlation	1	.966
	Sig.	-	.000
	N	334	334
Sexual Harassment	Pearson Correlation	.966	1
	Sig.	.000	-
	N	334	334

From table 3, the correlation coefficient between alcohol addiction and sexual harassment is .966. This indicates a positive correlation, implying that alcohol addiction leads to sexual harassment. Hence, the tendency for an alcohol addict to engage in sexual harassment is very high.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significance difference between the mean ratings of male and female undergraduates of Enugu State University on the correlation between alcohol addiction and sexual harassment among students of the University.

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Table 4: t-test analyses for hypothesis 4.

Variables	N	\bar{X}	SD	df	t-cal	t-crit	Decision
Male	183	2.53	0.64	332	-0.31	<u>+1.96</u>	Not significant (Do not reject hypothesis)
Female	151	3.24	0.68				

The t-test result in table 8 shows the t-calculated value (-0.31) is less than the t-critical value (+1.96) at a df of 332 and a confidence level of 0.05. Based on the decision rule no significant difference was found in the mean ratings of male female undergraduates of Enugu State University on the correlation between alcohol addiction and sexual harassment among students of the University.

CONCLUSION

Alcohol addiction is a chronic and potential fatal problem to human behaviours and societal peace. The data collected and analyzed on the study showed that alcohol addiction to a great extent leads youth (undergraduate students) to many anti-social behaviours that hinder socio-economic good interpersonal behaviour among people. The findings indicated that alcohol addiction leads male and female undergraduates of Enugu State University to a great extent in rival group classes, and sexual harassment.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, it was therefore recommended that;

- Government should increase its effort in public enlightenment on alcohol addiction and abuse among the undergraduate students.
- Tertiary Institutions management should make rules or regulation against alcohol and other dangerous substance for the undergraduate students.
- Guidance and counsellors should discourage the students from taking excessive consumption of alcohol and mount more enlightenment programmes to educate the undergraduate students.

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